

**З ПЕРЕКЛАДАЦЬКОГО ДОСВІДУ ІНТЕГРУВАННЯ УКРАЇНЦІВУ
ПОЛІКУЛЬТУРНЕ СЕРЕДОВИЩЕ РЕСПУБЛІКИ МОЛДОВА /
FROM THE TRANSLATION EXPERIENCE OF INTEGRATING
UKRAINIANS INTO THE MULTICULTURAL ENVIRONMENT
OF THE REPUBLIC OF MOLDOVA**

Diana IGNATENCO, Lecturer, PhD

(“Alecus Russo” Balti State University, Republic of Moldova)

diana.ignatenco@usarb.com

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0151-2641>

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In the work of the Ukrainian Language and Culture Center of “Alecus Russo” Balti State University translation activities are of particular importance. However, the Center's main goal is scientific, didactic, cultural and educational orientation aimed at preserving, researching and promoting the Ukrainian language and culture of Ukrainians in Moldova, as well as fostering ties with Ukrainians in Ukraine within the particular conditions of living in the multilingual environment of Moldova, where Romanian and Ukrainian are among the primary functioning languages. In the process of comprehending cultural, literary, linguistic phenomena and historical events in the destinies of our peoples, translation activity plays a guiding role in creating an intellectual identity and forming public opinion. The Ukrainian translation of literary works of contemporary Bessarabian postmodernist poets, carried out by our authors in 2012, has strengthened the current Ukrainian-Romanian literary ties, revealing common guidelines and the development of both literatures. The Ukrainian-Romanian

translation has acquired particular resonance and significance in recent years, marked by tragic events in Ukraine. Romanian and Bessarabian poets and writers, journalists and publishers were among the first to actively respond, expressing a strong desire to be heard by Ukrainians in their messages of solidarity and support for the Ukrainian people in their struggle for independence. One of the first areas of focus was to meet the social communication needs of Ukrainian citizens, who were forced to leave their homes and seek refuge in Moldova. This led to the essential production of translated educational and didactic materials for children, textbooks for pupils, and phrasebooks for adults who had settled in Romanian-language environments. This activity has also become crucial for the Ukrainian population of Moldova, as the second-largest ethnic group in the country after the titular one, in providing opportunities to study in their native language. Intellectual communication was also supported by Bessarabian poets, who were among the first to respond to the tragic events in Ukraine. Their poetry not only concentrates human emotions, but also reflects on the processes that caused the disasters, their consequences, and the numerous human, cultural, spiritual, and material losses. This resulted in the emergence of Romanian poetry, translated by us into Ukrainian. Some of these texts were published in literary magazines in Moldova and Romania. A bilingual poetry edition is currently being prepared for publication. Cooperation with leading Moldovan online publications has also proven significant. For example, the Moldovan branch of the Romanian media outlet *Timpul* published our Romanian-language translation of an interview with the late Ukrainian poet Maksym Kryvtsov, along with translations of his poetry. Subsequent editions featured Romanian translations of texts by Andriy Lyubka and Oksana Shchur. A meaningful and encouraging translation experience is reflected in the Romanian-Ukrainian two-volume edition, a 15-year-long project exploring family roots and chronicling the history of a family united by both Ukrainian and Romanian heritage. Thus, the article presents the role and main results of the translation activities carried out by scholars of the Ukrainian Language and Culture Center of “Alecu Russo” Balti State University, which reflect the stages of life of our society in the XXIst century.